

An Atlas of Impossible Longing: A Study from the Green Perspectives

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Abstract

This article seeks to examine the relationship between man and his environment. Anuradha Roy portrays man as a part of an ecosystem. The characters in the novel are a part of an intricate system. Anuradha Roy shows that if man is to be complete and content, he should view himself as a part of the natural world. This article illustrates the eco-critical consciousness of the novelist and how the nature is treated in this novel. The novelist portrays characters as searching for comfort in the nature and characters grew with nature. The novelist presents nature as one of the characters in the novel.

Keywords: Intricate system, Natural world, Ecosystem, Nature.

Anuradha Roy, one of the well-known Indian women writers. She gained fame as a novelist. The novel *An Atlas of Impossible Longing* sets in the outskirts of Bengal, Amulya and his family lives in their big new home. Kamal and Nirmal are the two sons of Amulya and Kananbala. Nirmala's wife died during the childbirth and gave birth to Bakul. Mukunda, orphan boy is adopted, who helps Amulya.

Anuradha Roy in her novel, *An Atlas of Impossible Longing* describes about the relationship between the human beings and the nature through the portrayal of its characters. The novel begins with the life of Amulya in Songarh. Amulya is a family man with a young wife and two children. His family abandons the Calcutta life and lives in Songarh town where he can co-exist peacefully with nature. This decision to settle in Songarh was taken by Amulya himself because while Amulya came to visit the fort and the town, it gave energy to him and when Amulya walked over the little town he felt a connection with the town. The idea of living in the town came to him as a benediction. He was not stopped from thinking about Songarh and felt that his life would be completed if he would live in Songarh. He liked and wished to enjoy the silence in nature.

Anuradha Roy throughout her novel uses ruined fort and wilderness into the characters to show that how nature is interconnected with characters. The ruined fort and the forest in Songarh gave spirit to Amulya. As years passed the nature also grew with Amulya's family. The ruined fort was in broken condition and even in its ruined condition; fort gave a fresh and peaceful feel to him. A few walls and one domed watchtower, which were in the fort was enough to feed Amulya's fantasies.

Amulya has a very deep and strong relationship with nature and forest. He woke up early in the morning and enjoyed the cool air and purple sky and felt that the forest was his only solace. When he came to Songarh the place was filled with weeds and bathua. Now the place is grown with “soft carpet of droop grass” (67). Amulya has a garden too. There is also a kitchen garden, which is dark with trees. Tall jackfruit trees and green coconut trees, like the green patches of his cultivation, have left their despairing signs in the abundant lush greenery when the saplings were planted the twigs were with four or five leaves. After twenty years those saplings are thirty feet tall and the branches seek place in the sky which is not visible under their garden and the afternoon stillness is broken by the falling of fruits from the trees. He speaks to the plants and nature is the only true companion for him. He walks all around the garden and sits in the garden swing. Every day he inspects them tenderly and pats those making strokes and he sees the plants as if it were pet animals.

Amulya converts the wilderness into garden by clearing the weeds and planting fruit trees, flowering plants and creepers. He selects plants to grow in his garden, and disregard the pink Kachnar and orange become plants. He planted his garden with flowers that bloom in darkness which gleamed white in darkness and scent the night time air. He allowed only one coloured flowering plant, that is yesterday – today – tomorrow colour plant, in which the flower turns from purple to white over during days and spreads fragrance. The rest of the garden was filled with pure white flower, *Magnolia grandiflora*, a plant which spreads its creamy petals against the shining green leaves. He also grows *Jasminum pubescens*, *Jasminum sambac*, *Nyctanthe sarbortrists*, and *Cestrum nocturnum*. The earth, Anuradha Roy presents, is one where little things matter.

Amulya finds solace in nature. At times when he was filled with thought he failed to notice the changes in nature. He also found solace in the ruined fort, the fort comforted him and gave him spirit and the nature calmed his mind. Amulya was on his way to the ruined fort. It comforted him to sit soundless among the fallen stones, thinking of nothing in particular waiting for his sense of calm to return. The fort was his ivory tower; he went to it whenever he needed to think anything through in solitude. Perhaps it was the suggestion of evanescent empires, the gaittiness of centuries. Old stone or perhaps the memory of people who, in those ruined rooms and dark passage, had lived lives as real as his own. It might have been the twisted grey-brown bark of tree with its suggestion of the Buddha's face.

Amulya reached the rim of the fort and sat on a block of fallen stone, a tall, greying, angular figure watching the blue shallow pool at the edge, which at that time of year had some water still. The folds of his dhoti spilled wave like on this stone, lifting a little at times in the breeze, picking up the dust which he did not notice. When the sun began to set the birds would know and began to call out each other. He willed himself to listen to the birds and think of nothing else. After the death of Amulya the garden was left unnoticed and it went back to wilderness, the garden was tended for a time but by an itinerant garden who had to be sacked after it was found he who nurturing a flourishing failed of cannabin in a sunny corner. Soon the grass was knee-high again and wild bushes of berries at the edges were attracting birds and noisy monkeys.

Anuradha Roy gives the relation between humans and the natural world in literature and how characters behave when they are in harmony with wilderness. Nature is represented as a comfort to the characters in the novel. Kananbala wife of Amulya also has relationship with nature. Kananbala is a house wife, who had to be in her house all alone, there was no neighborhood and there is no one to talk to her. So Kananbala wanted to disappear into the trees. She looked out through the window the moonlit trees. Once Kananbala and Larissa Barnum, the neighbourhood white lady went to the ruins of the fort. Kananbala though she is mentally ill she walked fastly to the old stone walls, touched the stone and saw the enormous banyan tree with hundreds of aerial roots. Barnum liked nature and said “Thus tree is supposed to bring people peace. It certainly does me” (81).

Kananbala was filled with happiness and her smile was filled with radiance. When she saw a shallow pool of water she ran towards the water like a child. She sat dipping her toes and let the feet slide in the water. In the ruined fort Mrs. Barnum tells the background of her life. But Kananbala was unable to understand anything.

Anuradha Roy represents characters as a peace gives. The physical and geographical settings in the novel also intermingled with nature and characters. Nirmal, son of Amulya and Kananbala also interested in garden who also went to Songarh ruins. Excitement and happiness filled Nirmal when he walked into the ruins. While Nirmal was in the ruins he also accepted the birds as part of the nature. Nirmal went to Rajasthan as a part of his job. He liked the desert sky in Rajasthan.

Anuradha Roy portrays pet animals and birds in the novel. The pet animals and birds also play a part as a character in the novel. It is to discover the roles have been played by literature in the ecology. Nirmal grew a pet dog, and he did not want to leave his dog alone. His wife is Shanti, who is also interested in growing plants. She named her daughter "Bakul". She was named by the tree which was found near her room. Bakul was also interested in gardening from her childhood. Mukunta another character in this novel named his son as "Gowtam", he named his son after the Banyan tree in Songarh ruins. Meera, a widow who was in Songarh to look after Bakul, was interested in feeding animals. She walked all the way to the ruins to feed the stray dogs, she felt bothered about the dog's foe those days when she did not come to feed the dog. When Meera decided to leave Songarh and go to new place she came to take a last look at the ruined fort and also to see the dog and its pups for the last time. Nirmal and Meera thought that the dog's family would be waiting for her every day. Meera also liked walking to the beautiful places in Darjeeling there were beautiful places to walk and had hills, beautiful orchids.

Suleiman Chacha, was the history teacher and house owner. Mukunda stayed in his house. Suleiman Chacha grew a parrot called Noorie. It looked as all parrots do, bright green, with a scarlet-purple band around the neck which seemed to be able to swivel a full circle as it watched people from its cage. Every night, Suleiman Chacha would cover the cage with a cloth, all the while muttering to the bird in a coaxing tone he used only with it. During the day, Chacha and Chachi would take turns to tempt the bird with curly green chillies and grain. The cage was large with a swing in it, which was kept in the wide upstairs verandah overlooking the trees, so that "Noorie could envy her free compatriots at leisure" (189).

Suleiman Chacha loved the parrot so much that the bird was let fly free in the house. He after completing his morning prayers goes to the cage and left cloth "with a flourish, making chucking noises at the bird" (189). The bird too loved the family and it responded to the family with a series of clicks of its beak and a soft word or two. Suleiman Chacha had taught the bird to say his name and half a dozen of other words. "As parents do with young children, he would coax the bird into speech for his visitors" (189). Suleiman and Noorie had been together every morning. Mukunda and Noorie had a good relationship. Noorie talked to Mukunda and he felt that Noorie was his constant companion: "It was only to her that I could confide how my success made me" (205). It would be on the door or on Chacha's shoulder or in Mukunda's shoulder.

Suleiman Chacha and Chachi decided to leave Calcutta. Chachi brought crisp green chillies and half a kilo of the grain which the bird liked to eat. Chachi said to Mukunda, "You know the sound Noorie makes when she wants a Chilli don't you?" (191). Suleiman Chacha asked Mukunda to keep the cage clean and talk to Noorie every morning: "Talk to her every morning, before you leave for work. She will be lonely with nobody in the house. She's not used to it" (98). After Suleiman Chacha and Chachi left the house parrot did not come out of the cage.

Barababu, Shanti's father and Mukunda's father-in-law, once he came to Suleiman Chacha's house. Barababu looked at the garden and as soon as they entered the house Barababu jumped to the corner and climbed up in the mango tree. He said that you don't know how much my soul longs for this. He said in rapture, looking down through a fringe of leaves on a high branch. "The village, our trees, the fruits I plucked as a boy" (195). Through these it is evident that Barababu, a minor character in the novel also portrayed as a lover of nature.

In another one incident Anuradha Roy made her character found comfort in nature. Mukunda went to Nirmal house. His heart beats uncomfortably and he wanted to slow down his breathing and calm him. So he looked back into garden, and saw "A madhabilata was in full flower on one of the walls. It had not been there before – a pink flowering intrude in the garden of whites. The mango trees had grown and small green fruit were visible even at a distance" (222). Mukunda walked into the garden and wandered towards the well. The white jasmine next to it was still there, still scattering the water with its flowers. He felt that it was a beautiful garden filled with old fruit trees, fragrant bushes and creepers. The incidents in this novel illustrate the ecocritical consciousness of the novelist and how nature is treated in this novel.

Work Cited

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